

CASE REPORT**RARE CASE OF PANCREATITIS**

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ABSTRACT:

Ascaris lumbricoides is one of the most common intestinal parasites world-wide and although the infection can be asymptomatic, in some cases it can present with complications, such as acute pancreatitis. We describe a case of 32 year old female who presented to the Emergency Department with acute upper abdominal pain with constipation for 5 days, fever for 3 days and vomiting for 2 days. Her family is running an Orphanage in Trivandrum with a total number of 32 inmates majority of them being from North Indian states. On examination, she had agonising pain, tenderness in the epigastrium, bowel sounds were sluggish. There was leucocytosis, elevated amylase and lipase levels, hypoalbuminaemia. Ultrasound showed inflammatory changes in the pancreatic body with peripancreatic free fluid, confirmed by plain CT and MRI abdomen. The patient was given intravenous antibiotics. On day 6 of hospital stay, the patient developed loose stools followed by an episode of vomiting. Her vomitus contained a single adult female *Ascaris* worm. Stool routine examination was normal. The patient was started on Albendazole. Oro-gastro-duodenoscopy showed a lax LES with antral erythema and an adult female *Ascaris* worm was seen invading the ampulla of Vater and was retrieved. 2 weeks later she coughed out an adult male worm. A repeat Stool routine examination showed fertilized eggs of *Ascaris*. Ascariasis is a rare cause of pancreatitis. The pathogenesis of *Ascaris* induced pancreatitis is that of the obstructive one and due to the “wanderlust” of the worm. When a patient presents with clinical features of pancreatitis, a possibility of *Ascaris* induced pancreatitis should be thought of.

KEYWORDS- *Ascariasis, Pancreatitis, Roundworm***INTRODUCTION:**

Ascaris lumbricoides, the largest of the common nematodes affecting humans, is the most common intestinal parasite world-wide and, although the infection can be asymptomatic, in some cases, it can present with complications, such as acute pancreatitis. The adult worm normally lives in the small intestine. Because they have ‘wanderlust and tend to explore ducts and cavities, they often invade bile or pancreatic ducts.[2] The most endemic areas are Asiatic countries such as India, and other developing countries. In the Indian subcontinent, ascariasis is highly endemic in Kashmir (70%), Bangladesh (82%), and central and southwest India (20-49%).[1] We describe a case of 32 year old female who presented to the Emergency Department with complaints of acute abdominal pain, who was diagnosed to have acute pancreatitis. After a considerable period of hospital stay, the aetiology was found to be ‘roundworm’ infestation.

CASE REPORT:

A 32 year old female who is married and living with her husband and their one-and-half year old child

presents to the Emergency Department of Dr. Somervell Memorial CSI medical college, Karakonam – a tertiary centre in South Kerala, with complaints of severe upper abdominal pain of acute onset. There was associated constipation of 5 days duration, fever of 3 days duration and multiple episodes of vomiting of 2 days duration. Her family is running an Orphanage in Trivandrum with a total number of 32 inmates comprising of children, elderly and mentally challenged persons, majority of them being from North Indian states. No history of similar complaints in the past. There was no h/o ethanol abuse or intake of food with high fat content. History suggested that the family undergoes regular deworming at 6 months interval along with the inmates of the institution but since the last one and a half years the patient was not any regular medications and no deworming was done. There was no family history of pancreatic diseases. At presentation, the patient had agonising upper abdominal pain and was restless in the supine position. Abdominal examination revealed diffuse tenderness along with guarding and rigidity. There was no organomegaly or free fluid. Bowel sounds were

sluggish. Laboratory investigation revealed leucocytosis(16070 cells/cu mm), elevated amylase (819/IU/L) and lipase (2447 U/L), hypoalbuminemia (2.82 g/dl) TSH – 0.06IU/ml . Transabdominal Ultrasound showed Inflammatory changes in the pancreatic body with peripancreatic free fluid(Figure 1). CBD and gall bladder were normal without any dilatation, wall thickening or calculus. Plain CT abdomen was taken and findings confirmed. In addition the scan showed inflammatory changes of the tail of pancreas, moderate ascites and bilateral pleural effusion(Figure 2). CECT abdomen was deferred due to the concern of contrast induced thyroid crisis. MRI abdomen done and features of necrotising pancreatitis ruled out. The patient was admitted in the intensive care unit where intravenous antibiotics (Piperacillin and Tazobactam) and supportive measures were given. On day 6 of hospital stay, the patient incidentally noticed passage of worms after an episode of loose stools. Following that the patient developed vomiting and the vomitus contained a single adult ascaris worm which was 18 cm long(Figure 3). It was morphologically a female worm confirmed by microbiologist. Stool routine examination, done on two consecutive days and the second sample revealed

fertilised ova. The patient was given a stat dose of Albendazole. Supportive management for pancreatitis continued. The patient was now started on Mebendazole 100 mg orally twice a day for 3 days and 500 mg orally once for another 3 days. The patient improved significantly over the next 6 days. Oesophago-gastro- duodenoscopy was done on day 9 and it showed a lax LES with antral erythema and Ascaris worm was seen invading into the ampulla of Vater(Figure 4). Endoscopic retrieval was done. Relook OGD showed no further evidence of Helminthic infestation. The retrieved worm was confirmed by the microbiologist as morphologically male and was 15 cm in length(Figure 5). Review Ultrasound done before the discharge showed a decrease in the pancreatic body size and reduction in the ascites as compared to the previous scan. Serum amylase and lipase levels had also fallen significantly in 12 days' time. She was started on clear fluids and on tolerating them well she was slowly switched to soft diet. She was discharged with oral mebendazole 500 mg once daily for 3 days and reviewed 2 weeks later in the OPD. She was asymptomatic and tolerating orally well.

Figure 1- inflammatory changes with peripancreatic fluid collection

Figure 2- inflammatory changes of the tail of pancreas, moderate ascites

Figure 3- Adult female roundworm in vomitus

Figure 4- Ampulla of Vater being invaded by adult worm ; ERCP finding

Figure 5- Endoscopically retrieved adult male worm

DISCUSSION:

The largest intestinal nematode, *Ascaris lumbricoides* is one of the most common causes of infection among the soil-transmitted helminths (STH).[1] Common in the tropics and sub-tropics, it is estimated that more than 25% of the world population is infected with *Ascaris*. [21,22] Most of the ascaris infected people are asymptomatic.[5] Our patient presented with typical clinical and biochemical features of acute pancreatitis. In certain parts of our country, ascariasis is second only to cholelithiasis as a cause of pancreatitis.[19] According to the findings made by *Khuroo et al*, *A. lumbricoides* is the etiological factor for 36.7% of patients with hepatobiliary diseases[2], 23% of patients with acute pancreatitis[6], 14.5% patients with liver abscesses[4] and 12.5% patients with biliary lithiasis.[3] Therefore, a fair majority of people with hepatobiliary and pancreatic ascariasis (HPA) present with features of acute pancreatitis. HPA can cause six distinct clinical presentations including[10]: biliary colic, acute cholangitis[11], acalculous cholecystitis[12,13], hepatic abscess[4], acute pancreatitis[7,14,15], recurrent pyogenic cholangitis.[3] There is a higher risk of infection in non-endemic areas due to the increased rate of migration and travel.[23,24] In our case, she was the supervisor of an orphanage which sheltered around 32 paediatric, mentally challenged and senior citizens most of them being immigrants from North India. Diagnosis can be made by ultrasonography, duodenoscopy and ERCP.[13,16] In our patient, Ultrasonography was suggestive of acute inflammation but the diagnosis was confirmed by plain CT and MRI. A CECT would have delineated the anatomy and complications better but in view of a possibility of contrast induced thyroid crisis, only plain CT was taken. Endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography is the gold standard method for identifying and removing the nematode from the duodenal, biliary or pancreatic tract.[27] In this case, one of the worms was retrieved during ERCP while it was seen invading ampulla of Vater. Of late, MRI and MRCP can help in the diagnosis of HPA and may replace ERCP, however MRCP is not therapeutic.[17,18] One female adult *A. lumbricoides* worm inhabiting the small intestine can produce approximately 200,000 eggs per day.[26] This makes retrieval from a stool examination easier. The best diagnostic test is still the stool examination for ova and parasites, diagnosed if large oval brown trilayered eggs with a mamillated coat are seen.[25] The stool can be negative for ova while the worm migrates and matures (approximately takes a month time)[25] Only when worms are mature do they start secreting eggs. Sometimes an adult worm can be seen passed per rectum or coughed up or passed in the urine.[25] Here, 2 worms were identified, one in the

vomitus and one identified during ERCP. The female worm can produce both fertilised and unfertilised eggs. When both female and male adult worms coexist, as in our case, the females produce fertilised eggs that are passed into the stool, which again gets ingested through contaminated soil and the cycle is repeated. The examination of stool sample of our patient showed fertilised eggs. However, though these nematodes have high 'wanderlust', invasion of the pancreatic duct is rare, probably due to its smaller caliber(6). Even then, even a partial migration into the duct is sufficient enough to produce inflammation. Worm remnants in the pancreatic duct may calcify and may cause recurrent pancreatitis.[20] Patients with pancreatic ascariasis may rarely end up having severe necrotizing pancreatitis, which may be fatal.[6,7,8] Necrotizing pancreatitis can be diagnosed by CECT abdomen and MRI abdomen and may rarely require surgical intervention if necessary. Anthelmintic drugs which are effective include pyrantel pamoate, mebendazole, albendazole and ivermectin.[5] In our case at the time of the diagnosis of ascariasis, a stat dose of Albendazole was given followed by a 6 day course of Mebendazole. The patient showed significant improvement with this regime. At 2 weeks follow up, after taking a further 3 day course of Mebendazole she was completely asymptomatic and doing well with oral diet.

CONCLUSION:

Many prospective studies and case series studies, in fact around 300 studies, have been published worldwide on *Ascaris* induced pancreatitis. Therefore a prompt elicitation of travel history, residential details of the person and a high degree of clinical suspicion of ascariasis should be there before a diagnosis of pancreatitis is made.

REFERENCES:

1. Khuroo MS. Hepatobiliary and pancreatic ascariasis. *Indian J Gastroenterol*. 2001;20:C28–32
2. Khuroo MS, Zargar SA. Biliary ascariasis. A common cause of biliary and pancreatic disease in an endemic area. *Gastroenterology*. 1985;88:418–423.

3. Khuroo MS, Dar MY, Yattoo GN, Khan BA, Boda MI, Zargar SA, Javid G, Allai MS. Serial cholangiographic appearances in recurrent pyogenic cholangitis. *Gastrointest Endosc.* 1993;**39**:674–679.
4. Javid G, Wani NA, Gulzar GM, Khan BA, Shah AH, Shah OJ, Khan M. Ascaris-induced liver abscess. *World J Surg.* 1999;**23**:1191–1194.
5. Pawlowski ZS. Ascariasis. In: Warren KS, Mehmoud AF, editors. *Tropical and Geographical Medicine*. 2nd ed. New York: McGraw-Hill; 1990. p. 369.
6. Khuroo MS, Zargar SA, Yattoo GN, Koul P, Khan BA, Dar MY, Alai MS. Ascaris-induced acute pancreatitis. *Br J Surg.* 1992;**79**:1335–1338
7. Wani NA, Bazaz MR, Ahmed MI, Peer GQ. Biliary ascariasis with worm-induced pancreatitis. *J Indian Med Assoc.* 1990;**88**:320–321.
8. Maddern GJ, Dennison AR, Blumgart LH. Fatal ascaris pancreatitis: an uncommon problem in the west. *Gut.* 1992;**33**:402–403.
9. Khuroo MS. Ascariasis. *Gastroenterol Clin North Am.* 1996;**25**:553–577.
10. Khuroo MS, Zargar SA, Mahajan R. Hepatobiliary and pancreatic ascariasis in India. *Lancet.* 1990;**335**:1503–1506.
11. Khuroo MS, Mahajan R, Zargar SA, Javid G, Banday M. Endoscopic vs surgical drainage of biliary tract in acute pyogenic cholangitis: a controlled study. *Indian J Gastroenterol.* 1989;**8**:119.
12. Mani S, Merchant H, Sachdev R, Ranavavare R, Cunha N. Sonographic evaluation of biliary ascariasis. *Australas Radiol.* 1997;**41**:204–206.
13. Khuroo MS, Zargar SA, Yattoo GN, Dar MY, Javid G, Khan BA, Boda MI, Mahajan R. Sonographic findings in gallbladder ascariasis. *J Clin Ultrasound.* 1992;**20**:587–591.
14. Shad JA, Lee YR. Pancreatitis due to *Ascaris lumbricoides*: second occurrence after 2 years. *South Med J.* 2001;**94**:78–80.
15. Tortajada-Laureiro L, Oliveira-Martín A, Marín-Serrano E, Ruiz-Fernández G, Eun JH, Segura-Cabral JM. Biliary parasite (*Ascaris*) as a cause of acute pancreatitis. *Ultrasound diagnosis. Rev Esp Enferm Dig.* 2012;**104**:389–390.
16. Bhushan B, Watal G, Mahajan R, Khuroo MS. Endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatographic features of pancreaticobiliary ascariasis. *Gastrointest Radiol.* 1988;**13**:327–330.
17. Adaletli I, Selçuk D, Gülşen M, Savaş C, Korman U. MRCP findings of biliary ascariasis before and

- after medical treatment. *Turk J Gastroenterol.* 2005;**16**:98–101.
- 18.** Ding ZX, Yuan JH, Chong V, Zhao DJ, Chen FH, Li YM. 3 T MR cholangiopancreatography appearances of biliary ascariasis. *Clin Radiol.* 2011;**66**:275–277.
- 19.** Parenti DM, Steinberg W, Kang P. Infectious causes of acute pancreatitis. *Pancreas* 1996;**13**:356–371
- 20.** Krige JE, Lewis G, Bornman PC. Recurrent pancreatitis caused by a calcified *Ascaris* in the duct of Wirsung. *Am J Gastroenterol* 1987;**82**:256–257
- 21.** de Silva NR, Chan MS, Bundy DA (1997) Morbidity and mortality due to ascariasis: re-estimation and sensitivity analysis of global numbers at risk. *Trop Med Int Health* 2: 519–528.
- 22.** Scott ME (2008) *Ascaris lumbricoides*: A review of Its Epidemiology and Relationship to Other Infections. *Annales Nestlé* 66: 7–22.
- 23.** Sklyarova VO. [Epidemiological features of parasitary invasis in women of reproductive age with disorders of reproductive health]. *Wiad Lek.* 2018;**71**(3 pt 2):674-677.
- 24.** Sklyarova VO. [Epidemiological features of parasitary invasis in women of reproductive age with disorders of reproductive health]. *Wiad Lek.* 2018;**71**(3 pt 2):674-677.
- 25.** de Lima Corvino DF, Horrall S. Ascariasis. [Updated 2022 Jul 18]. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2022 Jan
- 26.** Bethony J, Brooker S, Albonico M, Geiger SM, Loukas A, Diemert D, et al. Soil-transmitted helminth infections ascariasis, trichuriasis, and hookworm. *Lancet.* 2006 May;**367**((9521)):1521–32.
- 27.** Misra SP, Dwivedi M. Clinical features and management of biliary ascariasis in a non-endemic area. *Postgraduate medical journal,* 2000;**76**:29–32.